

**ПРИСКОРЕННЯ ЗРОЩЕННЯ ПЕРЕЛОМІВ У ХВОРИХ З ПОЄДНАНОЮ
КРАНІО-СКЕЛЕТНОЮ ТРАВМОЮ: МІФ ЧИ НІ?
ACCELERATED FRACTURE HEALING IN PATIENTS WITH
CONCOMITANT NEUROTRAUMA: MYTH OR NOT?**

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Анотація. Клініцистам здавна відоме прискорення зрощення кісток при переломах у хворих з поєднаною краніо-скелетною травмою. Мета роботи полягала в пошуку та аналізі наукових публікацій, що підтверджують або спростовують це твердження. Більшість дослідницьких робіт виконана в експерименті на тваринах. Феномен акселерації виявлений також і в ретроспективних дослідженнях.

Abstract. Long-time clinicians are familiar with the acceleration of fracture healing in patients with the combined types of polytrauma. The aim of the study was to investigate recent publications that confirm or deny this statement. Most of the studies were *in vivo* stage. The phenomenon of acceleration has been proven as such in retrospective human studies.

Introduction. According to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), in the United States alone in 2020, more than 220,000 people were hospitalized due to traumatic brain injury (TBI) counting about 600 hospitalizations per day [5]. Taken with national statistics, TBI plays a key role in the structure of polytrauma, combined with about 47% of limb fractures [7]. Starting in the early 60th, the authors described the phenomenon of acceleration of bone healing in polytrauma patients [1,6]. However, the first qualitative review was made only in 2005 by Morley et al [9]. In his study, Morley could not confirm or deny is the phenomenon of acceleration taking a place[9]. In the last decade, the number of publications increased dramatically, although most of them were *in vivo* phase of the study [1,3,4,10].

Aim. To search and analyze recent publications to confirm or deny the phenomenon of accelerated bone healing in patients with neurotrauma.

Materials and methods. The publication search in the range last 10 years was performed by the NCBI PubMed database using keywords: "TBI"; "Fracture healing"; "Bone callus"; "Combined neurotrauma".

Results. 134 studies were found excluding studies with high bias risk due to study design. There are 9 prospective clinical studies, while 8 of the authors concluded that the stages of bone healing were shorter in time for patients with combined neurotrauma

compared to isolated fracture. Moreover, in the last 10 years, the results of at least 46 experimental studies have been published. 43 of those found increase not only in the callus size in the polytrauma group but also in mineral density.

Discussion. The authors noted that the acceleration mostly touched the period of soft callus formation: its size and calcification volume in the neurotrauma group was greater at X-rays [10,11]. The size of bone callus in patients with polytrauma was 40% larger on average according to Boes [3]. In our opinion, a small number of prospective clinical studies is explained by moral and ethical barriers to treatment and examination of patients with high mortality rates, as well as insufficient knowledge of pathophysiological aspects of the acceleration phenomenon [4,6,9,12]. Numerous animal studies proved the phenomenon of acceleration on the contralateral to TBI limb, at least in rodents[8]. Talking about the ipsilateral limb, in addition to the normal bone healing time, local osteoporosis was noted [2]. Wang et al. research showed that the heavier the CNS damage, the more pronounced an acceleration phenomenon [11]. Some studies proved the impact of the motor cortex on bone healing [1]. While several studies noted the osteoinductive abilities of the cerebrospinal fluid of patients with neurotrauma when it was administered to mice [3,6].

Conclusion. To date, the phenomenon of fracture healing acceleration in concomitant polytrauma has been proven by numerous animal models, but qualitative prospective studies are needed to give more evidence. Mechanisms of fracture healing acceleration require further studies to find its main factors which may be used in patients with delayed unions and nonunions.

Literature.

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Відомості про автора.

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